

USING LOCAL BREEDS TO ADD-VALUE TO MEAT PRODUCTS

Consuming products of local breeds contributes to their recovery and environment sustainability

THE WHAT AND WHY

Quality meat with silvopastoralism?

The use of local breeds fed with local woody perennial resources by using silvopastoralism produce a high-quality meat product with more added value than meat coming from intensive industrial production systems. Moreover, silvopastoralism is based on resources that are only used by these local adapted breed grazers. The calf diet is based on 90% breast milk, since they are breast-fed calves, whose mothers feed on woody perennials. Otherwise, these woody perennials use to be the main fuel for fires which make local breeds being considered as

an environmental-care breed, mainly linked to silvopastoralism. The local breeds of Galicia use the brand “100% Raza Autóctona” to allow the identification of local breed products by the final consumer. The “100% Raza Autóctona” (“100% local breed”) logo identifies that the offered product comes from a local breed and that it is registered in the local breed genealogical book. It is a trade mark of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture.

Local Bovine Breed grazing in a silvopastoral system. BOAGA

Raza autóctona 100% label. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Buy local products to recover local breeds

The production of products such as meat, wool, eggs, skin etc of local breeds is considered an environmental-responsible and sustainable production. Livestock management is carried out in accordance with the traditional and local practices adapted to each area where they are implemented. Moreover, these practices allow better beekeeping, that is linked to each territory management and plant biodiversity that produces a specific honey from the flowers with characteristic and inimitable flavour. Local breeds give us unique and inimitable products depending on each territory vegetation, having in mind that each territory delivers a local food production adapted to nature, being its

maximum expression silvopastoralism, where woody perennials are included. Thus, value chain is based on the correct identification of the local livestock breeds products through the “100% Raza Autóctona” logo but also on the identification of the specific territory they graze for the different Protected geographical indications (PGI) that exist in the Spanish or EU territory. BOAGA (Federation of native breeds of Galicia) and FEDERAPES (Federation of Spanish native breeds) are working, which disseminate in their respective websites all information related to native breeds (www.boaga.es and www.federapes.com).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727872.

Keywords: Bio-economy, olives, residues, bio-products

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Local breeds provide food and products of high quality based on silvopastoralism.
- The logo “100% Raza Autóctona” provides product and environment protection to local breeds and causes the increase of its numbers, therefore better preserving livestock genetic resources.
- Agroforestry systems are the future as it allows farmers to integrate local breeds, agricultural and forest farming systems, achieving a more sustainable and fire-free environment.

Local Bovine Breed grazing in a silvopastoral system. BOAGA

FURTHER INFORMATION

The logo “100% raza autóctona”. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food.
<https://youtu.be/SsvB-oqetxc>

Autochthonous breeds of Galicia. Federation of native breeds of Galicia - BOAGA. <https://vimeo.com/202783164>

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Increasing agroforestry systems should be based on all sector knowledge increase about environment value

The implementation of agroforestry (AF) systems with proper technical management, where local breeds play a fundamental role (given the rusticity and adaptation to their specific environments) and are able to provide great environmental, economic and social advantages for the specific sectors. The involvement and recognition of these systems by public administrations is important as well as by the general public and consumers. Specific regulations for these types of livestock production would help to involve more farmers to establish these silvopastoral systems.

Agroforestry systems with local breeds would help to solve economic, environment and social issues. These systems would help to create greater income in marginal areas usually linked to rural depopulation. Therefore, AF provides new opportunities to increase rural areas value, associated to the production of livestock based on AF resources. The preservation of the environment is carried out through the use of low inputs, while animals maintain natural areas with a minimal cost. In addition, forest fires risk is reduced.

Local breeds in extensive systems would also be favoured as their census increase due to genetic heritage improvement, fulfilling a FAO objective. Local livestock breeds are characterized by rusticity and adaptation to a specific environment as main strengths. The existence of several livestock species (cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, horses, poultry) allow us to graze any area with different species palatability and perform the most appropriate management for the territory based on different livestock species use.

Agroforestry implementation should be based on the involvement of all sectors of the value chain, from the recognition of public administrations, that provide regulations recognizing these systems, to the final consumer, who should demand these valuable products. It is vital to foster the multiple use of the lands based on the various products that the territory is able to deliver.